

New Coordinate Vacuum Solution in Cosmological General

Theory of Relativity

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Abstract: In the general relativity theory, we discover new vacuum solution by Einstein's gravity field equation. We investigate the new coordinate in cosmological general theory of relativity (CGTR).

Keywords: Cosmological General Theory of Relativity; Gravity Field Equation; New Coordinate Vacuum Solution

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1. INTRODUCTION

We solve new vacuum solution by gravity field equation in cosmological general theory of relativity.

New spherical coordinate is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} [dr^2 + V(t,r) \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}]$$

$$V(t,r) = C_1 (act + br)^2, \quad C_1 = \frac{1}{b^2 - a^2}$$

a, b, C_1 is constant, c is light's velocity. (1)

In this time, Einstein's gravity equation is

$$\begin{aligned} R_{tt} &= \frac{\ddot{V}}{V} - \frac{\dot{V}^2}{2V^2} \\ &= \frac{2a^2}{(act + br)^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{4a^2}{(act + br)^2} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{rr} &= \frac{V''}{V} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{V'^2}{V^2} \\ &= \frac{2b^2}{(act + br)^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{4b^2}{(act + br)^2} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\theta\theta} &= -\frac{\ddot{V}}{2} + \frac{V''}{2} - 1 \\ &= -C_1 a^2 + C_1 b^2 - 1 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{\phi\phi} = \sin^2 \theta R_{\theta\theta} = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{tr} &= \frac{\dot{V}'}{V} - \frac{\dot{V}V'}{2V^2} \\ &= \frac{2C_1 ab}{(act + br)^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{4C_1 ab}{(act + br)^2} = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

In this time,

$$V' = 2C_1 b(act + br), \dot{V} = 2C_1 a(act + br), V'' = 2C_1 b^2, \ddot{V} = 2C_1 a^2$$

$$A' = \frac{\partial A}{\partial r}, \dot{A} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}$$

2. NEW VACUUM SOLUTION IN COSMOLOGICAL GENERAL THEORY OF RELATIVITY

Hence, new vacuum solution is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left[dr^2 + \frac{1}{b^2 - a^2} (act + br)^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\} \right]$$

a, b, C_1 are constant, c is light's velocity. (7)

In this time, if r' is

$$r' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{b^2 - a^2}} (act + br)$$

As

$$dr' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{b^2 - a^2}} (acdt + bdr)$$

Or

$$dr = \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - a^2}}{b} dr' - \frac{a}{b} cdt \tag{8}$$

If new solution Eq(7) is inserted by transformation Eq(8),

$$dr^2 = \frac{b^2 - a^2}{b^2} dr'^2 - 2 \frac{a}{b^2} \sqrt{b^2 - a^2} dr' cdt + \frac{a^2}{b^2} c^2 dt^2 \tag{9}$$

In this time, if α_0 is

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{a}{b} \tag{10}$$

Hence, proper time $d\tau$ of new solution is

$$d\tau^2 = (1 - \alpha_0^2) dt^2 + 2\alpha_0 \sqrt{1 - \alpha_0^2} dr' \frac{dt}{c} - \frac{1}{c^2} [(1 - \alpha_0^2) dr'^2 + r'^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}] \tag{11}$$

In this time, if dt' is

$$dt' = \sqrt{1 - \alpha_0^2} dt \tag{12}$$

Therefore, new solution is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 + 2\alpha_0 dr \frac{dt}{c} - \frac{1}{c^2} [(1 - \alpha_0^2) dr^2 + r^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}] \quad (13)$$

If we rewrite dt, dr instead of dt', dr' , the proper time $d\tau$ of new solution is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 + 2\alpha_0 dr \frac{dt}{c} - \frac{1}{c^2} [(1 - \alpha_0^2) dr^2 + r^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}] \quad (14)$$

Therefore, new spherical solution in general relativity theory is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 + 2\alpha_0 dr \frac{dt}{c} - \frac{1}{c^2} [(1 - \alpha_0^2) dr^2 + r^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}]$$

$$\alpha_0 \neq 1, \quad \alpha_0 \text{ is constant} \quad (15)$$

In this time, the coordinate transformation in cosmological general theory of relativity [1-3] is

$$r \rightarrow r\Omega(t_0), t \rightarrow t, \quad (16)$$

t_0 is cosmological time. $\Omega(t_0)$ is the ratio of universe's expansion in cosmological time t_0 .

Hence, this vacuum solution is by the coordinate transformation in cosmological general theory of relativity,

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 + 2\alpha_0 \Omega(t_0) dr \frac{dt}{c} - \frac{\Omega^2(t_0)}{c^2} [(1 - \alpha_0^2) dr^2 + r^2 \{d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2\}]$$

$$\alpha_0 \neq 1, \quad \alpha_0 \text{ is constant} \quad (17)$$

3. CONCLUSION

In the general relativity theory, we discover new vacuum solution by Einstein's gravity field equation. We investigate the new coordinate in cosmological general theory of relativity.

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